

NEW ASPECTS RELATING TO THE BEHAVIOUR OF COMPOSITES AND ADHESIVES IN SPACE

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ABSTRACT

This paper addresses some of the specialized testing procedures and results performed in the Molecular Contamination Investigation Facility at Jet Propulsion Laboratory for the WideField Planetary Camera II (WFPC II) program for the screening of polymeric materials for outgassing properties. WFPC II poses some rather unique and stringent cleanliness requirements, crucial to mission performance, which result from the fact that WFPC II is being fabricated as an Ultraviolet-imaging science instrument. As such, WFPC II possesses very low levels of contamination-allowables. Hopefully, this testing will generate additional interest and continued research activity in this aspect of outgassing contamination.

KEY WORDS: Outgassing; Contamination; Testing/Evaluation; Composites; Adhesives

INTRODUCTION

Outgassing contamination has always been a serious concern for the proper operation of spacecraft in the hostile environments of space. Condensed outgassing substances can be detrimental to the proper operation of optics, thermal-control surfaces, solar cells, detectors and other vital components.

New space missions and new technologies pose even greater challenges upon both instruments and materials capabilities than ever before, with increased emphasis on outgassing behaviours.

WideField Planetary Camera II (WFPC II) science instrument will be used to replace the existing WFPC I unit which is already in orbit aboard the Hubble Space Telescope. The latest directives from NASA have assigned this new WFPC II instrument (being designed and fabricated at Jet Propulsion Laboratory/California Institute of Technology) to be built as an Ultraviolet detector for optical imaging (i.e., Far-Ultraviolet performance). This means that the levels of contamination-allowables for molecular contamination now become absolutely crucial to mission success (most outgassing contaminants absorbing rather strongly in the Ultraviolet spectrum).

Additional renewed attention to outgassing comes from analysis of the recently retrieved NASA (National Aeronautics and Space Administration) LDEF (Long Duration Exposure Facility). And the most recent information from Magellan indicates higher levels of surface contamination occurring than expected. In addition, current (start-up) experience with EOS project (Earth Observational System) suggests that this program will also have stringent outgassing requirements.

Shown below is a depiction of the Graphite/Epoxy-Composite Optical Bench fabricated for WFPC by Boeing Aircraft Co. This structure (with related adhesives) is of particular concern from a contamination-control standpoint because this structure lies in the immediate vicinity and critical path of the Charge-Couple-Device (CCD) imaging detectors. Therefore, any outgassing contaminants that are generated from this structure can not easily be "vented" to the outside of the craft (as can some of the other outgassing sources).

WIDEFIELD PLANETARY CAMERA

For WFPC II, a science performance goal of 1% photometric accuracy at 1470 Angstrom over an extended time (at least 30 days) has been established.¹ This means that the contamination-control task is extremely critical to the success of WFPC II and has required re-evaluation of the entire manufacturing and assembly process.

To complicate matters, the WFPC II instrument is utilizing the newest technology involving CCD detectors (capable of imaging in the wavelength region of 1200 - 10,000 Angstroms). This poses even more stringent requirements since this device will operate at a temperature of -100 C, thus making this device a very effective "getter" for the condensing of volatile materials onto the Magnesium Fluoride windows of the CCDs (and thus reducing the instrument Far-Ultraviolet "throughput" efficiency).

Unfortunately, the CCD's happen to be extremely sensitive to very low levels of molecular contamination in short-wavelength imaging. An additional related disadvantage with the use of CCD technology relates to the fact that the device is extremely sensitive to temperature, such that it can not be effectively warmed beyond very limited temperature excursions (i.e., in an attempt to "drive-off" collected contaminant materials by intermittent warming to higher-temperature exposures).

BACKGROUND

Recognizing the importance of understanding outgassing behaviour, NASA and ASTM (American Society for Testing and Materials) have well-established test protocols in place for conducting measurements, and also for compiling resultant outgassing information for many materials (e.g., Johnson Space Center SP-R-0022A and ASTM-E-595). The standard "Micro-VCM" test, now ASTM-E-595, was originally developed through joint research by JPL/Stanford Research Institute. These procedures have led to the well-established spacecraft "requirements" of 1% maximum TWL (Total Weight Loss) and 0.1% maximum VCM (Volatile Condensable Matter).

These test methods were developed in order to accomplish the rather "impossible" mission of defining a relatively "quick-and-easy" test method for determination of extended-life behaviour of materials in the hostile space environment. Thus the test is carried out at a sample temperature of 125 C (in order to simulate both an "abbreviated" aging condition and a "worst-case scenario") - and with a collector plate at ambient temperature for 24 hr period. However, the test temperature of 125 C is excessive for many polymeric systems which begin to exhibit some degree of degradation at temperatures even below this level. Also, exposure to this elevated temperature can/ will effect additional crosslinking/ postcuring for thermosets, which may inappropriately affect test results for these materials.

These particular test methods possess other serious drawbacks, including the fact that these methods can

not discern any correlations between TWL levels observed and resultant VCM levels obtained. Thus, it does not necessarily follow in actual practice that a material with high weight loss will also exhibit high levels of condensables, or vice versa (especially when solely utilizing a room-temperature collector plate for measurements). Further, standard TWL and VCM data is somewhat misleading in that those materials which prove to be "preferred materials" (i.e., per SP-R-0022A/ ASTM-E-595) may not in fact be "acceptable" materials for use in specialized applications below 20 C (viz., optical applications), or for extended exposure times, higher temperatures, or effects of thermal-cycling, etc.

Conventional test methods and cleanliness standards for material screening, hardware fabrication and assembly-level test and integration are inadequate for instruments which require a stable Far-Ultraviolet performance. New spacecraft requirements call for an enhanced/ expanded test method to monitor the following:

- A) quantitate the collectibles at -100 C, -50 C, -20 C (i.e., versus time and sample temperature)
- B) "real-life", actual-operating-temperature data
- C) analysis of the exact nature of effluents emanating from the sample material
- D) determination of the phenomenon of surface desorption from the sample materials versus true "outgassing" from bulk-diffusion mechanisms
- E) re-volatilization ("desorb") behaviour of collected species from contaminated surfaces when those surfaces are subsequently warmed
- F) condensing rates versus time (and at varying sample temperatures)
- G) modeling of data to predict whether the sample source can effectively 'clean-up' (deplete) the volatile components - and an analysis of the times, temperatures and conditions required in order to accomplish this task

The analysis and interpretation of this type of outgassing data is a necessary step in the prediction of the WFPC II instrument performance and for the process of improving it.

BASIS FOR TEST PROCEDURE

Prior experience has shown that thermal-vacuum conditioning can effectively reduce TWL. "High-temperature" thermal-vacuum will reduce it even more (although improperly-cured and improperly-mixed adhesive materials exhibit unacceptable TWL and VCM levels even after extended thermal-vacuum conditioning).⁴

Prior analysis and review of VCM thickness versus transmittance data demonstrated that an allowable of 1%-throughput degradation at 1470 Angstroms translates into an allowable VCM thickness of about 15 Angstroms (which is in the range of one monolayer for some molecular outgassed species).³

More specific to the WFPC II program, "optical-degradation-allowable" implies that a 15 MHz (1.56×10^{-9} g/cm² Hz) TQCM* may increase in frequency only a little more than an average of 3 Hz per day over a 30-day period. At another observation wavelength of interest (1216 Angstroms) the allowable VCM is even less.³

Note: data on VCM thickness versus time and the transmittance of various VCM versus wavelength performed by Martin-Marrietta Corporation under contract to JPL.

DESCRIPTION OF TEST METHOD

The test set-up basically consists of a tightly-controlled vacuum chamber which utilizes polished stainless-steel sample cup holders (1.5 inches diameter x 2 inches deep).

The sample is placed in a heat-exchanger assembly with a shutter mechanism to "isolate" the sample until such time as the chamber "background" has cleaned (or at least stabilized). Prior to the testing of each sample, the Molecular Contamination Investigation Facility (MCIF) chamber is checked for the background contamination level. During each background treatment, as well as during each sample run, the MCIF chamber is monitored continuously for sample temperature, TQCM* temperatures, vacuum pressure, contaminant deposition, and residual gas with the aid of *Thermal Quartz Crystal Microbalances (TQCMs) and Residual Gas Analyzer (RGA) sensors.

Normal procedure (i.e., JPL procedure) is to subject the sample materials sequentially to 20 C, 40 C, and 70 C outgassing temperature levels in vacuum environment (to 10^{-8} Torr), followed by a repeat exposure to a lower temperature level in order to apply some mathematical determinations/extrapolations as to the degree of "improvement" gained from the 70 C exposure.

The condensable materials from the material samples at each of the temperature levels are collected and measured by the use of three TQCMs (maintained at -20 C, -50 C and -100 C). The RGA (mass spectrometer) is used to supplement the TQCM data.

Each sample temperature exposure is followed by a "desorption" step to determine the amount of residual condensate remaining (as "non-removable" contamination) on the TQCMs when these crystals are then warmed to appropriate temperatures.

This test procedure is performed not only on material samples, but on actual subassemblies as well.

The anticipated benefit of this test effort will be to identify those materials (and assembly details) which pose a true outgassing contamination hazard - and additionally, to determine whether it appears that these materials and assemblies can be further processed/conditioned (or otherwise altered) to reduce that risk.

DRAWBACKS

It is recognized at the outset that there are several serious drawbacks to this test regime:

- > Surface-area-to-volume ratio of the sample configuration is probably critical to the results
- > Because of the polar chemical nature of epoxies (as an example), the exact chemical nature of the surface of the epoxy when cured "against" an air interface will not be the same as that of an epoxy surface as cured against metal (as in a sandwich configuration)
- > Sample preparation is no doubt crucial to the results obtained (i.e., mix procedures, exact mix ratios used, exact cure schedules used, etc.)
- > Lack of optical effects (transmittance) data (i.e., some collected substances may be more deleterious to optical performance than other substances, even at identical accumulated mass levels - or may absorb only at specific Ultraviolet wavelengths).
- > There is no provision for the effects of UV, which may well cause synergistic effects upon the sample, as well as upon collected substances *
- > Likewise, effects of atomic oxygen presence are not observed in this test (as encountered in low-earth orbit) *
- > The test results will necessarily need to extrapolate condensible tendencies and behaviours onto other kinds of surfaces
- > This test regime is necessarily limited in exposure times. It is recommended that the expected/assumed behaviour at extended exposure times be empirically verified

- > The test samples are prepared in a uniform manner as far as sample weights, sample configurations, etc. (in order to obtain comparable data). However, this does not necessarily faithfully represent "real-life" usage conditions or amounts
- > Acceptable use, even of "good" materials, will also depend upon such other factors as proximity and line-of-sight to critical surfaces, actual weight amounts anticipated for use, exposed surface areas, whether the material can be "effectively" overcoated (or utilized in a diffusion-limited sandwich configuration), operating temperature for that particular assembly, whether the material is hermetically sealed or else otherwise effectively baffled within a detail assembly, etc.
- > From initial test results it appears that obtained data may be highly variable and dependent upon specific batch lots for a given material (although reproducibility of repeat testing with same-batch/ same-mix is excellent)
- > Questions arise as to whether the samples should in fact be preconditioned first, before MCIF testing
- > Several other shortcomings require judicious interpretation of the data

** [these properties will be tested in detail under actual space environments aboard EOIM-3 (Evaluation of Oxygen Interactions with Materials) scheduled for launch January, 1992.]*

RESULTS OF MCIF TESTING - FOR GY70/ FIBERITE 934 AND FIBERITE 7714 COMPOSITE MATERIALS (AND RELATED ADHESIVES)

BACKGROUND MONITORING (This analysis is run before each particular sample run. The following is presented as typical "background" behaviour)

16 Jan, '90 Background run with chamber at 70 C

-100 C	TQCM stabilizes to zero slope (or zero collection rate*)	at [20.2] hr (272 Hz total increase)
- 50 C	" " " " " " " "	2 hr (4 Hz " ")
- 20 C	" " " " " " " "	0 hr (0 " ")

Note: values in brackets and corresponding total Hz values are calculated, extrapolated values.

** [or else the re-volatilization rate exists in equilibrium with the condensing rate at this particular point]*

The RGA (Residual Gas Analyzer) displayed the following initial peaks as AMUs (atomic mass units) with the following chemical species characterized as "best guess" at this point:

<u>Major peaks</u>	<u>Minor peaks</u>	
1 AMU (H· ?)	<3> AMU (HD, H ³)	<51>
2 " (H ₂) [D]	<4> " (He)	<52> (CH ₂ F ₂)
[15] " (CH ₃) [CH ₄ fragmt]	[12] " (C) [CO or CO ₂ fragmt]	[53]
[16] " (CH ₄) [O as O ₂ /CO frag]	[13] " (C-H?)	[54]
[17] " (NH ₃) [OH-? as H ₂ O frag]	[14] " (N?)	[56]
[18] " (H ₂ O) [NH ₄ + ?]	<19> " (F)	[58] (Acetone)
[26] " (C≡N?) [HC≡CH? LiF?]	<20> " (HF?) [Ar++ Ne]	<61>
28 " (N ₂) [CO? CH ₂ =CH ₂ ?]	<24> " (C ₂ as oil fragmt, Mg)	65
[29] " (CH ₂ =NH) [-COH? CH ₃ CH ₂ ?]	<25> " (H-C≡C:) C ₂ H as oil frag	[67]
[30] " (H ₂ C=O) [NO?]	[31] (CH ₂ OH) [CF P]	

	CH ₃ CH ₃ ?		[68]
[39] "	(NaNH ₂) [K? NaOH? C ₃ H ₃]	<32> "	(O ₂) [CH ₃ OH? S?]
[41] "	(CH ₃ -CH=CH)	[37] "	(HCl) (Cl ³⁷)
<43> "	(H-CON) [C ₃ H ₇ CH ₃ CO]	[38] "	(F ₂ ?) [HCl ³⁷]
[55] "	(Mn)	[40] "	(Ar) [SiC? NaOH? CH ₂ =C=CH ₂]
[57] "	(CH ₂ COCH ₃)	[44] "	(CO ₂) [H ₂ COCH ₂ epoxide?]
	CH ₃ CHO acetaldehyde? SiO?		<73>
		[45] "	(SiOH) [CH ₂ CH ₂ O]
			<83>
			<84>
		<47> "	(·CH ₂ CH ₂ F) [C-Cl ³⁵]
		<49> "	(·CH ₂ Cl)
			[86]
		<50> "	(CH ₃ Cl) [CCl ³⁷ CF ₂ Freon]
			87

(Note: AMUs in brackets eventually decrease significantly. AMUs in <> disappear altogether eventually.)

The background RGA spectrum eventually achieved the following status before sample run:

Major Peaks	Minor Peaks
-----	-----
2 AMU	[12] AMU
[15]	[14]
[16]	[26]
[17]	[27]
18	[29]
28	40
[44]	

SUMMARY OF BACKGROUND DATA (FROM NUMEROUS RUNS)

BACKGROUND APPEARS TO REQUIRE ON THE ORDER OF 20 HR AT 70 C TO STABILIZE/DEplete*, AND PERHAPS ~2 HR AT 107 C TO DEplete. (RECOMMENDATION IS FOR FURTHER VERIFICATION OF THE 107 C DATA.)

* Note: [i.e., the term depletion referring to "apparent depletion". Test data on material samples shows that when "revisiting" prior sample temperature levels (after 70 C exposure), additional condensation is observed. It is recommended that further testing be specifically designed to verify whether this is a result of the fact that this particular test protocol does not allow "complete" depletion to occur before changing temperature conditions - or whether these are "newly-formed" degradation products from the 70 C exposure which are being observed.]

SAMPLE RUN 7714 COMPOSITE (AS CURED 260 F 90 MIN + 160 F FOR 8 HR)

Sample Temp at 20 C (19 hr total run time)

-100 C TQCM attains zero rate at [32] hr (& 14 Hz increase)[13 SMW]*
- 50 C " " " 8 hr (& 1 " ") [1 MMW]
- 20 C " " " 0 hr (& 0 " ") [0 HMW]

* SMW = "Small" Molecular Weight (Based on observation that this fraction collects only below -50 C)
MMW = "Medium" Molecular Weight (i.e. collects below -20 C)
HMW = "High" Molecular Weight (i.e. collects at -20 C)

*Note: all three TQCMs have identical "view factor" to sample.
Hz levels reported per gram of sample weight.*

[Ratio of collectibles: -100 C/-50 C/-20 C = 93%: 7%: 0%]

Warming the -100 C TQCM (for 6 hr at -46.9 C) seems to have no effect on removal of collectibles, as evidenced by the fact that bringing this TQCM back down again to -100 C regains the identical Hz level which is observed just before warming (TQCM Hz output is temperature-dependent, so that comparisons must be based upon Hz levels obtained at identical TQCM temperatures).

SUMMARY OF TEST DATA FOR 7714 AT 20 C

SAMPLE AT 20 C REQUIRES ~ 32 HR TO EFFECTIVELY DEplete (LONGER THAN THE 23 HR SEEN WITH 934 COMPOSITE). RGA SHOWS NO NEW AMU PEAKS FORMING (I.E., AS DIFFERENT FROM OBSERVED BACKGROUND SPECIES).

SAMPLE TEMP INCREASED TO 40 C (55 minutes stabilization of chamber at temperature before start of data collection [with sample material "isolated" from main test chamber] - then 16 hr total run time)

-100 C TQCM zero slope at	[23] hr (& 13 Hz increase)	[11 SMW]
- 50 C " " "	12 hr (& 2 " ")[2 MMW]
- 20 C " " "	0 hr (& 0 " ")[0 HMW]

[Ratio of collectibles: -100 C/-50 C/-20 C = 85%: 15%: 0%]

Warming the -100 C TQCM to -46.9 C for a 6-hr period seems to effectively "lose" 100% of these collectibles.

Bringing the -50 C TQCM up in temperature for 6 hr to -20 C achieved initial Hz starting level before collection of condensibles (apparently 100% loss of collectibles).

Note: [TQCMs are set to approximately -50 C (for the -100 C TQCM), -20 C (for the -50 C TQCM) and 12 C (for the -20 C TQCM) and sample temperature set to 0 C as a standard "desorb" procedure between runs.]

SUMMARY OF TEST DATA FOR 7714 AT 40 C

SAMPLE AT 40 C REQUIRES ~28 HR TO DEplete (MUCH SHORTER THAN THE 87 HR REQUIRED FOR 934-COMPOSITE). RGA SHOWS DECREASING ACTIVITY LEVELS FOR C AND NH₃*. THE CHROMATOGRAM SHOWS MAJOR AMUs H₂, He, H₂O, N₂, Ar AS UNCHANGING OVER THE RUN.

* (i.e., as "best guess" as to species identification)

SAMPLE TEMP INCREASED TO 70 C (55 minutes to stabilize chamber temperature - and then 16 hr total run time)

-100 C TQCM zero slope at [26] hr (& 23 Hz increase)[20 SMW]
 - 50 C " " " 8 hr (& 3 " ") [3 MMW]
 - 20 C " " " 0 hr (& 0 " ") [0 HMW]

[Ratio of collectibles: -100 C/-50 C/-20 C = 87%: 13%: 0%]

SUMMARY OF TEST DATA FOR 7714 AT 70 C

SAMPLE AT 70 C REQUIRES ~53 HR (SHORTER THAN THE 70 HR FOR 934-COMPOSITE). RGA SHOWS THAT THE FOLLOWING SPECIES INCREASED IN ACTIVITY: NH₃, OXYGEN, CH₃, H₂O, H₂C=O, Ar.

SAMPLE TEMP CYCLED BACK DOWN TO 40 C (55 minutes to stabilize at temperature - and then 16 hr total run time)

-100 C TQCM zero slope at [24] hr (& 9 Hz increase)[9 SMW]*
 - 50 C " " " 0 hr (& 0 " ") [0 MMW]
 - 20 C " " " 0 hr (& 0 " ") [0 HMW]

[Ratio of collectibles: -100 C/-50 C/-20 C = 100%: 0%: 0%]

* [originally 11 SMW and 2 MMW were observed during the first test exposure at 40 C]

FIBERITE 7714 SAMPLE TEMP CYCLED BACK TO AMBIENT

Monitoring the RGA with sample brought to ambient temperature shows noticeable increases in AMUs 12, 16 (4X), 17 (4X), 18 (3X), 32 (2X), 44 (3X). The following AMUs decreased significantly: 15, 20, 27, 29, 30, 40. (AMU 3 disappeared).

SUMMARY OF TEST DATA FOR 7714 WHEN AMBIENT TEMPERATURE REVISITED

BRINGING THE SAMPLE BACK TO AMBIENT CONDITIONS SHOWS THAT AN ADDITIONAL 24 HR CONDITIONING PERIOD IS NECESSARY (SHORTER THAN THE 73 HR SEEN FOR 934-COMPOSITE). THE FOLLOWING SPECIES WERE SEEN BY RGA TO INCREASE IN ACTIVITY LEVELS: C, CH₄, NH₃, H₂O, O₂, Ar. THE FOLLOWING WERE SEEN TO DECREASE IN ACTIVITY: CH₃, HF, H-C=N, CH₂=NH, H₂C=O, CO₂.

SAMPLE RUN - FIBERITE 934 COMPOSITE (OPTICAL BENCH) ["extended cure" at 275 F + 11-21 thermal cycles at Boeing]

Sample Temp at 20 C (17 hr total run time)

-100 C TQCM zero slope at [22.2] hr (& 16 Hz increase)[16 SMW]
 -50 C " " " 0 hr (& 0 " ") [0 MMW]
 -20 C " " " 0 hr (& 0 " ") [0 HMW]

[Ratio of collectibles: -100 C/-50 C/-20 C = 100%: 0%: 0%]

Warming the -100 C TQCM (for 6 hr at -45.7 C) seems to "lose" only ~ 5.1% of the original collectible material, as evidenced by the fact that bringing this TQCM back down to -100 C does not effect much change in the final -100 C Hz level.

SUMMARY OF TEST DATA FOR GY70/934 AT 20 C

SAMPLE AT 20 C REQUIRES ~ 23 HR TO EFFECTIVELY DEplete (LONGER THAN THE 18 HR SEEN WITH EC 2216 (FOR COMPARISON), BUT IDENTICAL TIME AS SEEN FOR EA 9394). DURING DESORB, CH₄ AND CO₂ APPEAR TO BE DECREASING, BUT OTHER SPECIES APPEAR TO BE ON THE INCREASE (NH₃, H₂O, N₂, O₂). THIS WOULD TEND TO INDICATE THAT THE CH₄ AND CO₂ ARE INDEED EMANATING FROM THE SAMPLE (?)

GY70/934 SAMPLE AT 40 C

Sample Temp at 40 C (16 hr total run time)

-100 C TQCM zero slope at [87] hr (& 22 Hz increase)[22 SMW]
 - 50 C " " " 0 hr (& 0 " ") [0 MMW]
 - 20 C " " " 0 hr (& 0 " ") [0 HMW]

[Ratio of collectibles: -100 C/-50 C/-20 C = 100%: 0%: 0%]

Warming the -100 C TQCM ("Desorbing" for 6 hr at -45.7 C) seems to "lose" only ~ 4.6% of the original collectible material, as evidenced by the fact that bringing this TQCM back down to -100 C nearly regains the previous final Hz level.

SUMMARY OF TEST DATA FOR GY70/934 AT 40 C

SAMPLE AT 40 C REQUIRES ~87 HR TO DEplete - WITH 22 HZ TOTAL COLLECTION (LONGER THAN THE 19 HR SEEN WITH EC 2216, OR THE 28 HR SEEN FOR EA 9394). THIS THEN, SHOWS A LONGER TIME REQUIREMENT FOR "CLEAN UP" OF THIS MATERIAL AT THE HIGHER TEMPERATURE.

Sample Temperature Increased to 70 C

Sample Temp at 70 C (16 hr total run time)

-100 C TQCM zero slope at [70] hr (& 27 Hz increase) [27 SMW]
 - 50 C " " " 0 hr (& 0 " ") [0 MMW]
 - 20 C " " " 0 hr (& 0 " ") [0 HMW]

[Ratio of collectibles: -100 C/-50 C/-20 C = 100%: 0%: 0%]

Warming the -100 C TQCM ("Desorbing" for 4 hr at -25 C and then warming the TQCM to -11.4 C over 2-hr period) seems to "lose" ~ 7.7% of the original collected material.

SUMMARY OF TEST DATA FOR GY70/934 AT 70 C

SAMPLE AT 70 C REQUIRES ~70 HR TO DEplete, AGAIN A LONGER TIME REQUIREMENT THAN AT 20 C. OXYGEN, NH₃, H₂O, N₂, Ar, HF, C≡N, HC≡N APPEAR TO INCREASE IN ACTIVITY.

GY70/934 Sample Temperature Back Down to 40 C

Sample Temp at 40 C (16 hr total run time)

-100 C TQCM zero slope at [73] hr (& 30 Hz increase)	[30 SMW]
- 50 C " " " " " 0 hr (& 0 " " " " ")	[0 MMW]
- 20 C " " " " " 0 hr (& 0 " " " " ")	[0 HMW]

[Ratio of collectibles: -100 C/-50 C/-20 C = 100%: 0%: 0%]

SUMMARY OF TEST DATA FOR GY70/934 WHEN 40 C REVISITED

IT WOULD BE EXPECTED THAT THE MATERIAL WOULD HAVE BEEN "CLEANED UP" AT THE SAMPLE TEMPERATURE OF 40 C, BUT THERE IS STILL A SIGNIFICANT AMOUNT OF EFFLUENT (OR ELSE RESIDUALS AS DEGRADATION BY-PRODUCTS OF THE 70 C EXPOSURE), AS EVIDENCED BY THE 73 HR NECESSARY TREATMENT TIME AND 30 Hz TOTAL INCREASE.

THE OXYGEN LEVEL IS SEEN TO GRADUALLY DECREASE AT 40 C, AS DOES C, NH₃ AND H-C≡N. THE RECOMMENDATION IS MADE TO TAILOR THE TEST TO CONFIRM WHETHER THERE ARE "INITIAL" RESIDUAL SUBSTANCES EVEN AFTER THE 70 C EXPOSURE - OR WHETHER THESE ARE "NEW" DEGRADATION PRODUCTS BEING FORMED AT 70 C.

REPORTING OF THE DATA

Meaningful reporting/ tabulating of the data poses some very real difficulties. The data, as reported here, is in Hz-per-gram-of-sample-weight (paints/ coatings reported as Hz-attained-per-square-inch-of-sample-surface). However, if surface desorption is the predominant mode of outgassing during this relatively "short" test method (i.e., as opposed to bulk diffusion), then Hz per available surface area might be a better reporting criteria. An extended test procedure would probably better observe and confirm the diffusion behaviour of species to the sample surface.

Trying to tabulate a comparative data listing is made difficult because different criteria might be utilized. For example: desorb behaviour (i.e., subsequent re-volatilization of accumulated substances from the TQCMs when warmed) might be viewed as the "most" important "bottom-line issue". Or else a criterion might very well be based upon maximum molecular-weight allowable (as AMUs) for observed condensibles.

Finally, the total-time-and-temperature required to attain "total depletion" for each sample material is probably the only information of interest to those in the production arena.

	EC 2216	EA 9394	934 COMP	7714 COMP	RTV 566	CHEMGLZ	
Sample Temp.							
* -100°rate	1.1	1.4	0.4	1.2	0.8	6.8	
** Hz	69 Hz	43 Hz	13 Hz	11 Hz	35 Hz	682 Hz	
20°C - 50°rate	0.7	0	0	0.3	0	0	
Hz	14 Hz	0 Hz	0 Hz	2 Hz	2 Hz	3 Hz	
- 20°rate	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Hz	7 Hz	0 Hz	0 Hz	0 Hz	0 Hz	0 Hz	
-100°rate	7.4	1.7	0.5	0	1.5	2.8	
Hz	179 Hz	68 Hz	9 Hz	11 Hz	35 Hz	682 Hz	
40°C - 50°rate	0.2	0	0	0.3	0	0	
Hz	22 Hz	0 Hz	0 Hz	2 Hz	2 Hz	5 Hz	
- 20°rate	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Hz	4 Hz	9 Hz	0 Hz	0 Hz	1 Hz	0 Hz	
-100°rate	16.1	1.9	0.5	1.1	3.8	2.3	
Hz	146 Hz	123 Hz	11 Hz	20 Hz	81 Hz	249 Hz	
70°C - 50°rate	3.4	0	0	0.5	0.8	0	
Hz	17 Hz	0 Hz	0 Hz	3 Hz	19 Hz	22 Hz	
- 20°rate	2.7	0	0	0	0	0	
Hz	3 Hz	12 Hz	0 Hz	0 Hz	5 Hz	8 Hz	
-100°rate	9.2	-	-	-	-	-	
Hz	978 Hz						
107°C - 50°rate	2.7						
Hz	76 Hz						
- 20°rate	0.2						
Hz	19 Hz						
Time req'd	@ 20°C	18 hr	23 hr	22 hr	32 hr	26 hr	16 hr
	@ 40°C	19	39	87	23	69	14
	@ 70°C	21	53	70	27	70	16
	@ 107°C	162	-	-	-	-	-

* (rate of collection at 16 hr)

** (total Hz increase, extrapolated in some cases)

	EC 2216	EA 9394	934 COMP	7714 COMP	RTV 566	CHEMGLZ	
Highest M.W.	@ 20°C	46	44	44	44	44	44
	@ 40°C	46	44	44	44	44	44
	@ 70°C	92	44	44	44	44	44
	@ 107°C	93	-	-	-	-	-
Book TWL	.88-1.93	-	.40-.58	-	.08-.41	1.18-2.04	
Book VCM	.01-.09	-	.00-.09	-	.00-.03	.01-.37	
Measured TWL	1.39	1.89	0.98	-	0.07	4.7	
TWL-WVR	(0.36)	(0.23)	(0.32)	-	(0.05)	(4.3)	
Measured VCM	.04	.02	.00	-	.00	.06	
Deposit	lt opa	none	none	-	none	opaque	

EFFECT OF WARMING THE TQCM TO RE-VOLATILIZE CONDENSABLES
 ("rem" = % removed)

Mat'l	EC 2216	EA 9394	934 COMP	7714 COMP	RTV 566	CHEMGLZ
Sample Temp @ 20°C						
-100° TQCM	-	100% rem.	5% rem.	0% rem.	100% rem.	100% rem.
- 50° TQCM	-	100% rem.	N/A	?	100% rem.	100% rem.
- 20° TQCM	-	100% rem.	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Sample Temp @ 40°C						
-100° TQCM	-	100% rem.	5% rem.	100% rem.	100% rem.	100% rem.
- 50° TQCM	-	100% rem.	N/A	100% rem.	100% rem.	100% rem.
- 20° TQCM	-	0% rem.	N/A	N/A	100% rem.	N/A
Sample Temp @ 70°C						
-100° TQCM	35% rem.	% rem.	8% rem.	75% rem.	75% rem.	66% rem.
- 50° TQCM	-	% rem.	N/A	66% rem.	70% rem.	60% rem.
- 20° TQCM	-	% rem.	N/A	N/A	68% rem.	73% rem.
Sample Temp @ 107°C						
-100° TQCM	25% rem.	-	-	-	-	-
- 50° TQCM	-	-	-	-	-	-
- 20° TQCM	-	-	-	-	-	-

DATA REDUCTION AND MODELING

In order to fully understand the nature of the outgassing contamination phenomenon, modeling of the data is necessary. This has several approaches, and many assumptions and estimations. A mathematical model is desired for characterizing kinetically the condensable materials observed. This requires estimation of source-emission time constants for each separate entity, required in order to predict an effective bake-out protocol. Thus the process of modeling involves characterizing each material by a source-rate and activation energy, by a re-emission rate-constant during accumulation, and by a desorption-rate/ emission-rate constant (and associated activation energy) during desorption. One major problem here is the scarcity of background literature data and directly-applicable published test data.

There are equations and computer programs for modeling changes in optical properties for reflectance and transmittance (a reasonable model of UV absorption is exponential behaviour in relation to contaminant deposition thickness).⁵ The results from this kinetics modeling and the optical effects modeling must then be utilized in the equations derived to form the transport-mechanism model (i.e., of volatile-condensables to critical surfaces) for the particular spacecraft. This transport mechanism analysis entails geometric considerations to determine surface temperatures, and critical line-of-sight from all pertinent outgas sources. Still, there remain additional issues regarding "return flux", mean-free-paths, self-scattering, particle trajectories, etc.

For pure materials, the Langmuir-Knudsen equation is used to describe kinetic behaviour:^{4,5}

$$m = 5.83 \times 10^{-2} P_v(M/T)^{1/2} \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$$

P_v = vapor pressure in Torr (at temperature T)

M = molecular weight

T = temperature, K

Of course, this equation requires molecular weight and vapor pressure for each specific substance and at specific temperatures. However, very few of the many materials used in spacecraft have determined molecular weights and vapor pressures - one of the problems being the high degree of (relatively unknown) "impurity" levels and mixtures which comprise most polymeric materials.

For desorption behaviour (i.e., outgassing as a purely surface phenomenon), the following equation is used to determine the mass loss rate (as might be applied to coatings and paints):^{4,5}

$$m = \sum_j k_{n,j} \left[a_{0,j} \sum_{t_{n-1}}^n \int (m_{n-1} dt_{n-1}) \right] e^{-k_{n,j} t_{n,j}}$$

$k_{n,j}$ = rate constant at temperature T_n for j^{th} component

$a_{0,j}$ = initial mass available of j^{th} component

$m_{n-1} = k_{n-1} a_{0n-1} e^{-k_{n-1} t_{n-1}} \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$

$t_{n-1,j}$ = duration of time that temperature is T_{n-1} for j^{th} component

n = n^{th} time interval where temperature is T_n

For purely bulk-diffusion-outgassing mechanisms, the following equation is used to describe mass-loss rate (from Fick's Law):

$$M_S(t > t^*) = -W_S (8/\pi^2) \sum_{i=1}^N \mu_i K_{di} e^{-k_{di} t}$$

W_S = total mass of material

μ_i = active component i mass fraction

$k_{di} = 2D_i/4h^2$

D_i = diffusion coefficient for the i^{th} component

h = source coating thickness

For the more "real-life" case, where the volatile substances are distributed "uniformly" throughout the source material and have some definable mobility through the molecular network, a more sophisticated diffusion model is needed to characterize the kinetic behaviour by bulk-diffusion - also "surface-residence time" and surface emission for each source component.

At this point, an approach needs to be devised to formulate an "accumulation-data model". Modeling equations speak of "capture coefficients" and "sticking coefficients" (as opposed to the classical "condensation coefficient") which represents the probability of an incident molecule "permanently" adhering to the collector/ receptor. Re-emission test data tends to indicate that the "capture coefficient" is independent of source or receptor temperature and can be defined by the classical "Knudsen theoretical accommodation coefficient". This "capture coefficient" is obtained as an empirical value (defined as the average fraction of the incident molecules which are "captured" by the surface) and is highly dependent upon many factors. (The "capture coefficient" is equivalent to "sticking coefficient" when re-emission is negligible.)

As a relatively simplistic case, a two-component model yields source/ component activation energy which permits extrapolation to lower flight temperatures:^{4,5}

$$f = f_0 + 1/k_v (df/dt)_v (1-e^{-v t}) + 1/k_n (df/dt)_n (1-e^{-k_n t}) \quad \text{for } t \ll 1/k_n$$

$\langle df/dt \rangle_i$ = initial (1 hour) average rate
 $\langle df/dt \rangle_f$ = final average rate at t_f final time
 when frequency change $f = f(t_f) - f_0$

Theoretical fit versus sample TQCM Hz data⁴

In order to adequately predict the effects of outgassing behaviour for a particular instrument/ spacecraft, re-emission kinetics needs to be adequately applied to subsequent re-volatilization of deposited contaminants ("desorption data model"), which appear to have rate constants different from those exhibited by the parent material. These re-emission rates can conceivably be affected by ultraviolet radiation, 'new' molecular interactions between collected species (also by the presence of electrons, protons, ozone, atomic oxygen, etc.). This analysis treatment is currently in progress for the WFPC II science instrument.

A proposal³ has been advanced by JPL to review this outgassing data as an ongoing testing protocol for the more "common" spacecraft materials, in order to formulate new criteria for quality-acceptance of polymeric materials for use in spacecraft fabrication along the following generalized guidelines:

- > LEVEL 1 STANDARD This would apply the existing, familiar ASTM-E-595/ SP-R-0022A standards - for spaceborne applications with no cooled sensors (or with no short-wavelength detectors)
- > LEVEL 2 STANDARD This would incorporate existing ASTM-E-595/ SP-R-0022A acceptance standards as a slightly modified test regime (incorporation of 75 C to 100 C sample temperatures, use of a -20 C collector plate, etc.). The application would be for missions accomodating sensitive, short-wavelength sensors (but not cooled)
- > LEVEL 3 STANDARD Based upon use of a single TQCM at 90 K and/or 170 K (this would not condense or measure water molecules, since presence of water is not always seen as a major issue). This standard would apply to those applications utilizing cooled sensors, but with a "large" acceptable contamination "budget" for operational performance requirements
- > LEVEL 4 STANDARD As a very stringent, controlled test regime, along the guidelines of WFPC II test procedures, for very sensitive optical devices and systems with cooled detectors

By analyzing and understanding the nature of outgassing phenomena, and by monitoring and measuring the species which are volatilized and the species which are collectible, we can then perhaps begin to examine/ monitor polymer systems more carefully (for quality-control acceptance). Further, we may even be able to scrutinize the ingredients of selected systems with a view towards formulating/ preparing our own "clean" customized systems for specialized use.

The MCIF data, while still being evaluated, does appear to indicate that most of the polymeric systems tested can be "cleaned" (at least to a large extent). The data has in some cases yielded some surprising results (promulgating additional questions in the process), but has generally contributed some valuable, preliminary criteria regarding materials which are judged to be acceptable for use in specified locations and applications on the WFPC II science instrument.

Further testing and analysis of the voluminous data will result in optimized properties and performance for polymeric systems in space applications, and will thus help to achieve improved instrument capabilities for future missions.

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